

Assessment Of Climate Change Vulnerability On Kerala's Agriculture

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Abstract

Climate change is now affecting every country in every continent and it is disrupting national economies and affecting lives around the world. Climate change-related vulnerabilities are extremely large in the state of Kerala. Extreme weather events such as temperature rise and irregular monsoons have developed into catastrophic unanticipated calamities like floods, landslides, and droughts, that are now life-threatening. These changes will have far-reaching consequences for the agriculture sector of Kerala.

Keywords: Climate change, Agriculture, Temperature, Rainfall

Introduction

Climate change is a major worry since it has a negative impact on people's quality of life around the world in general and on agricultural production and food security for the farming community in particular (Sani S and Chalchisa T,2016). Emission of Greenhouse gases (GHGs) increases temperature, which in turn creates unpredictable weather, such as flash floods and drought, as well as an increase in sea level. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) estimates that, compared to the period between 1850 and 1900, the global surface temperature would rise by 1.5°C by 2100(IPCC,2013). Extreme events are also anticipated to occur more frequently in the future. Agriculture will be impacted by these global climate changes both directly and indirectly through their impact on crops, soils, livestock, and pests. Malnutrition and deficiencies in micronutrients will result from increased climate change-related threats to food security at 2°C or higher global warming levels (IPCC,2022). These risks will be exacerbated by increases in the frequency, intensity, and severity of droughts, floods, and heat waves, as well as by continued sea level rise.

The state of Kerala is currently threatened by extreme climate events, despite being known for its moderate tropical environment. The previous few years have seen an increase in temperature, unreliable monsoons, and a water shortage in Kerala. However, in recent years, these have evolved into extremely dangerous unanticipated tragedies such as heavy rains floods, landslides, droughts, and tsunamis that will continue to haunt us. These unexpected calamities have had a significant impact on

the agriculture sector of Kerala. The state's paddy production was harmed by heavy monsoon rains in 2007, followed by unusual summer showers in March 2008. Seasonal crops and plantations were severely damaged across the state during the 2002 monsoon slack over Kerala. The most sensitive plants like black pepper, cardamom, coffee, tea, and cocoa are get affected due to increasing temperatures in Kerala.

Objectives

1. To understand the climate profile of Kerala
2. To assess the effect of climate change on agriculture Production in Kerala.

Data Source And Methods

The study is based on secondary data. Reports prepared by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, India Meteorological Department, the Department of Environment and Climate Change, Kerala, and Articles that lend support were reviewed to determine the effect of climate change on agriculture in Kerala. Line charts were used in analysing the climate profile of Kerala.

Results And Discussion

Extreme weather conditions like temperature rise and changes in the amount and distribution of rainfall adversely affected the production of food and plantation crops in Kerala.

1. Climate Profile of Kerala

Kerala experiences a tropical monsoon climate with heavy rainfall that occurs seasonally and sweltering summers. There are four seasons in the state 1) The hot season lasts from March until the end of May. 2) The South West Monsoon season followed, lasting until the start of October. The North East Monsoon season lasts from October to December, and the winter season lasts for two months in January and

February. Due to the presence of the Arabian Sea in the west, the state experiences exceptionally high humidity levels also (Department of Environment and Climate Change, 2014). The sections that follow provide information on temperature and rainfall.

1.1 Temperature

The state's average minimum and maximum temperatures range from 22 to 24 °C and 32 to 34 °C, respectively. The annual mean temperature varies by location, with the coastal belt experiencing a range of 25.5 to 27.5 °C, the middle region experiencing 27.5 to 29.5 °C, and the mountainous areas experiencing 17.5 to 21.5 °C. In the summer, the High temperatures cause the soil's top layer to dry out and create a drought situation.

1.2 Rainfall

Kerala is located in a tropical region with a lot of rain and humidity. The South-West Monsoon (June-October) and North-East Monsoon (October- December) are the two main rainy seasons in Kerala. In the state, the total yearly rainfall ranges from 360 cm in the far northern regions to roughly 180 cm in the southern parts. The state receives over 70% of its yearly rainfall during the southwest monsoon (June–October), which is the main rainy season.

The graph below displays the highest maximum and minimum temperatures as well as the heaviest rainfall amounts observed in Kerala's 12 IMD met observatories for the year 2021.

Source: Statement on climate for the state of Kerala:2021, ICCS

Source: Statement on climate for the state of Kerala:2021, ICCS

1.2 Effects of climate change on agriculture production in Kerala

Climate change could have an impact on agricultural production. If policymakers, agriculturalists, and crop breeders are to assure global food security, they must understand climate change (Zhao et al,2017). Kerala's agriculture is susceptible to climate change because of temperature increase and variations in the amount of water available, which can have a serious impact on crop production throughout the state's agro-ecological zones.

The impacts of climate change on rice have been intensively researched because rice is one of Kerala's most important crops. In

order to comprehend how meteorological variables, affect the production of the rice variety Jyothi, Aswathi, et al (2020) carried out an experiment at the Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi in the year 2019 -2020. The study indicated that increases in maximum and minimum temperatures were found to have a considerable detrimental impact on rice yield. Gopakumar C.S (2011) revealed that on the basis of long-term climate change, it is doubtful that the paddy productivity in Kerala during Kharif or Virippu will decrease due to rising temperatures, but it is likely to decrease significantly due to a protracted monsoon season, followed by extraordinary

summer rains. Additionally, rather than long-term changes in temperature and rainfall, plantation crops including tea, coffee, black pepper, cardamom, cocoa, cashew, and rubber are subject to climate variabilities like floods and droughts.

Joy, P. (2020) studied the Challenges of climate change on spice crops in Kerala. Black pepper, cardamom, nutmeg, ginger, turmeric, and clove were the major crops considered. The production loss in black pepper due to climate change is 10,700 tonnes, valued at 4,027 million INR at the 2018–19 market average prices. The loss in cardamom production is 6,600 tonnes valued at 6,795 million INR, or about 38.5% of the crop. The loss in quantitative terms for perennial tree spices like nutmeg and clove is estimated at 2,749 tonnes of nutmeg worth at 1,018 million INR and 13 tonnes of clove valued at 9.3 million INR. In the meantime, the two biannual rhizomatous spice crops, ginger and turmeric, have had crop losses of 20% and 15%, respectively. A total of 48,253 acres have been impacted, which has resulted in a loss of production of 25,138 MT of spices with a value of 12,541 million INR.

S Nair et al (2021) examined the impact of climatic variables on the output of black pepper in Idukki, Wayanad, Kannur, Kasargod, Kottayam, and Kollam, major pepper-producing districts of Kerala. It was determined from the study that the maximum and minimum temperatures had a major impact on the production of black pepper. With each unit increase in maximum and minimum temperature, there was a fall in production of 2.52% and 1.88%, respectively. The production of black pepper was also found to be negatively impacted by a unit increase in relative humidity and rainfall.

Another important spice grown in Kerala is cardamom. Murugan M, et al (2012) opined that young tillers and leaves of cardamom may completely wither if exposed to high daytime temperatures, which can reach 32°C. When combined with a protracted dry season, a relatively high air temperature during the cardamom flowering period (April to May) may result in less pollination and flower abortion. Rainfall, a significant climatic factor linked to climate change, has an impact on cardamom yield because cardamom is extremely sensitive to both excess rainfall and drought.

Conclusion

Agriculture is climate-sensitive, therefore, the output of important crops including paddy, pepper, coconuts, and rubber has been negatively impacted by climate change in terms of rainfall variability and temperature increase. Agriculture is vulnerable to climate change, therefore its effects would be more devastating in the future. So, in order to prevent or lessen the risk connected with climate change, strong public assistance is needed from the side of governments as well as from the side of research and technology.

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<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1701762114>